

**VILLAGE EXPANSION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BANTIAN
VILLAGE, PULAU HANAUT DISTRICT, EAST KOTAWARINGIN
REGENCY, CENTRAL KALIMANTAN, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

This study aims to find out which are the results after Bantian village was divided into new villages. After running for approximately six years, the expansion of the village can be evaluated to determine the extent of development in the village. The author limits his study on how was the development of basic services of the community in the fields of education, health, infrastructure, and general administrative services in the village. As the goal of regional expansion, which is a concrete form of decentralization and regional autonomy, and as a strategic step to improve the implementation of government duties in service and community empowerment towards a society that is advanced, independent, prosperous, just and prosperous. The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. This study involved the elements of society and organizers of Government in Bantian Village as the subject and object of this study. Data were obtained through interviews, secondary data from documents related to planning and development activities that had been carried out in Bantian village. Data analysis techniques used are interactive model analysis techniques. The results of the study show that the proliferation of Bantian village is the aspiration of the village community, which is determined by a decision by the authorized government organizer. In the implementation of the policy, the first thing that was felt by the community was the satisfaction, because the realization of their desires namely the Bantian hamlet and the surrounding area were determined to be a village. There was an increase in development compared to the previous situation, in addition to the increase in many other things that caused a sense of dissatisfaction with the community as a target. But even so, it is hoped that the community groups still have the confidence that all these obstacles will be overcome with a gradual time.

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1. Introduction

Regional expansion is a concrete form of decentralization and regional autonomy policy. This policy is a strategic step taken by the regional government to improve the quality of the implementation of the duties of local government in the context of service, empowerment, and development towards the realization of an order of life in an advanced, independent, prosperous, just and prosperous society. In other words, the essence of the expansion of the autonomous region is more emphasized in the aspect of government services to improve the welfare of the community. Therefore, regional expansion is one way or approach to accelerate regional development acceleration.

Sabarno (2007) states that the policy formulation of regional expansion is much outlined in existing government policies, both in law, government regulations and the regulations below. These regulations generally state that the purpose of forming, eliminating and merging is intended for the welfare of the people. Various opinions on regional expansion, among them Pambudi (2003) explain, regional expansion is to expand the range of services and create new impetus from the community for the emergence of an established initiative towards mutual independence, therefore if there is a regional expansion policy, the policy must provide guarantees that government officials have the ability to maximize government functions. Khairullah and Cahyadin (2006) that regional expansion is one of the government's efforts to improve the quality and intensity of services. To have a balance between one another, the formation of new regions needs to pay attention to the availability of resources. This needs to be done so that there will be no disparity among others in the future. The regional expansion will create a public space which is the collective need of the new region expansion which will further affect the activities of people or communities who benefit because they will obtain services from the new government because of the closer resources.

On the other hand, there are many arguments from various groups that support regional expansion. Whereas regional expansion aims to shorten the range of government service control, opening development inequalities/disparities between regions and creating regional economies, to achieve public welfare. Regional expansion is expected to bring services to the community closer, increase community empowerment and enhance development to prosper the community. Furthermore, another reason for regional expansion is the effort to develop local democracy through the distribution of power at a smaller level.

Village expansion is one form of expansion of the new autonomous region, developing as a way to increase development at the village level and improve people's welfare. The enactment of Law No. 06 of 2014 concerning Villages will significantly change the realization of village income, because the village will get funding from the Central Government and the Regional Government. This will certainly be an opportunity for the village to improve the welfare of the village community through

development programs at the village level, therefore government officials in the village must have sufficient capacity to maximize the functions of the village government, and create a new impetus in the community for the birth independent initiative towards village independence.

Based on the previous laws in a kind of village social structure, other indigenous peoples and so on have become social institutions that have important positions. The village is an autonomous institution with its traditions, customs, and laws. Village autonomy is genuine autonomy intact, round and not a gift from the central government or the Regional Government. Instead, the Government is obliged to respect the original autonomy of the village owned by the village.

According to Yunaldi (2008), village expansion is the breakdown of one village into two or more with consideration of the area, geographical conditions, population growth, effectiveness and efficiency of services to the public/community, and attention to social and political conditions. Theoretically, the expansion of villages in Indonesia is the formation of a new administrative area at the district level of the city from its parent. Empirically, the expansion of regions in Indonesia has happened a lot both at the provincial level, regency/city, district up to the village/sub-district level. Normatively there are laws and government regulations governing regional expansion.

Bantian Village is one of the villages resulting from the expansion of Bapinang Hilir Laut Village in 2011 in the Pulau Hanaut District, East Kotawaringin Regency, Central Kalimantan Province. This village was formed with Regional Regulation No. 06 of 2011, concerning the Establishment of eight definitive villages in East Kotawaringin Regency. The expansion of this area is based on the consideration to expand the implementation and dissemination of development in the Region to improve services to the community in East Kotawaringin Regency by taking into account the geographical location, area, population, number of villages/sub-district that meet the requirements stipulated in regional regulations.

Birth of East Kotawaringin Regency Regulation number 06 of 2011 is a new history for eight villages in East Kotawaringin Regency, including Bantian Village. The community of Bantian Village and its surroundings welcomed the results of the struggle of the village formation committee. This is a new milestone for Bantian Village which was previously designated as a definitive village as a result of the expansion of the village of Bapinang Hilir Laut.

Before being divided into a village, Bantian is a hamlet part of the village of Bapinang Hilir Laut. Bapinang Hilir Laut Village has a large area, large population and scattered patterns of a community settlement. This situation certainly makes it difficult for the village government to interact with the community and on the contrary, the village community also finds it difficult to interact with the village administration in various matters and needs. Village budgets disbursed from the Government can be said to be incompatible with the extent of the village area. Development activities are limited and more are done only in the village center so that the surrounding hamlets and

surrounding areas are rarely touched by development activities. This is the background of the proposed village expansion which is believed to be able to overcome these problems. With the hope that with the expansion of the village there will be an increase in services to the community, development activities will be further increased, so that the welfare of the community will be more quickly realized.

1.1 Research Problem

Based on the background of the problem, the formulation of the problem in this study is;

- 1) Can the expansion of the Bantian village area policy influence the improvement of services to the community, especially in terms of mandatory Government affairs in the fields of education, health, and regional infrastructure?
- 2) What are the obstacles in the process of providing services to the community?

2. Methods

The type of research used in this study is the type of descriptive research with a qualitative approach method. The focus of the research is the policy of village expansion on service to the community. There are four things that are the focus of attention if described in-depth, namely: 1) the effectiveness of the achievement of the objectives of regional expansion; 2) efficiency of the amount of effort needed to produce the level of effectiveness; 3) sufficiency, meaning that the alternatives can satisfy the needs, values or opportunities in resolving the problems that occur; and 4) responsiveness of a policy can satisfy the pretension needs, or values of certain community groups.

The research subjects were individual villagers in the research location, groups, and institutions related to the subject under study. This research was conducted in Bantian Village, Pulau Hanaut District, East Kotawaringin Regency, Central Kalimantan. The informants and research subjects were people related to the expansion of the village policy, namely Pulau Hanaut District, Bantian Village Community, and Policy Organizers.

The source of research data is taken from two types of data, namely primary and secondary data. Primary data is in the form of interviews with several informants who are considered by competent researchers to provide accurate data. Secondary data in the form of documents, legislation, records, documentation files, and all forms of information obtained either as information or data from previous research results by other people. The process of collecting data is done through observation, interviews, and field documentation. The technique used is a qualitative analysis technique according to Miles and Huberman in Sugiyono (2008) through three stages of analysis, namely data reduction, data presentation, and attract conclusions.

3. Results

3.1 Village Expansion Policy towards Efforts to Improve Services to the Community in Education Sector

Education is an important part of public service. Based on the observations of researchers, the problems in the field of education before and after becoming a village were problems with the availability of educational facilities and infrastructure which included educators, and physical facilities and infrastructure, as well as the absence of education at an advanced level. Other problems that also affect the implementation of education in Bantian village before the existence of the village division, the existing village road infrastructure facilities are not good enough to affect students' access to school. Community expectations are great through the expansion of the village to be able to see the improvement and development of educational facilities and other village infrastructure. The indication of the availability of educational facilities can be seen from the number of educational facilities available, the number of school-age children out of the total population of the village, and the number of children attending school by comparing before and after the village is divided.

Based on the results of observations, there was an increase in the desire of school-aged children and the comparison of school-age children with the number of children attending school had also increased. This shows an increase due to the existence of school facilities supported by improvements in village road infrastructure after the expansion of the village. After the expansion of the Bantian village, one junior and senior high school was built to confirm the educational needs in the region.

The availability of educators is one of the main elements in the success of education. Comparison of the number of teaching staff per student influences the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process, furthermore to increase the human resources resulting from the education process. After the expansion of the village, there was an increase in the number of teaching staff in the villages of Bantian, both civil servants and honorariums.

Based on the results of interviews with the Bantian Village Chief, there was an increase in the formal education sector both in terms of interest and participation of the community in their working area. Constraints in the field related to the problems of educational facilities were overcome by combined elementary and junior high schools in one location or commonly called a one-roof school. A local village leader also agreed that the development in Bantian village was felt by the surrounding community. As a result, the children in the village no longer need to go to school far from their villages and go to school in their villages. Complaints after the realization of this program only on educational facilities that is still inadequate. The surrounding community contributed in the form of land grants so that the school building could be quickly built by the local government. This statement was supported by the combined elementary and junior high school Principal in Bantian village that the proposal to the local

government had been made but there was no realization of development for separate schools so that the education process was not disrupted.

3.2 The Village Expansion Policy on Service Improvement efforts in the Health Sector

The existence of health facilities in a village is a must because health facilities such as Pustu, Posyandu, Polindes, in the village are part of basic infrastructure facilities in the village. Based on the results of direct observation in the field, there is one Pustu in Bantian village which was established in 2013 and one officer (nurse) assigned to this village by the East Kotawaringin Regency Government. The establishment of the Pustu and the assignment of health workers in this village is a necessity for the community in the village of Bantian. In addition to the existence of the pustu, with the authority of the village, the village government also established Posyandu at several points as an integrated health service post for the village community. This is intended to reach people who are still far from the village health service center. Even though the implementation is done once a month by cadres and health workers both from the pustu or from the puskesmas in the sub-district.

According to the head of the Bantian village, before the expansion in the village area, the community, if they want to seek treatment, should go to the main village far away. After the expansion of the village, the impact was the presence of health facilities and their officers. Constraints in the health sector in Bantian village are related to the geographical condition of the Bantian village, which is structurally separated from each other so that health services are constrained in village access. Besides, there is also an incomplete health function in existing facilities such as the unavailability of Poskesdes and midwives. Another complaint expressed by cadres of Bantian village health workers was the slow disbursement of the budget for cadre incentives and the cost of implementing additional feeding programs for children under five and elderly. The affordability of village officials to residents because of difficult road access has also become an unresolved problem. The local government has tried to build clean water facilities but because the amount is still limited so that the impact has not been felt by all villagers.

3.3 The Village Expansion Policy against Service Improvement Efforts in the Infrastructure Sector

Based on the results of observations in the field, there has been an increase in the condition of road and bridge infrastructure in the rural villages from the condition before and after approximately 4 years of division. Next, the researcher interviewed the Bantian Village Chief, he explained that the development in his village was built based on funding from the Provincial Budget, PNPM Mandiri, and the MP3KI Program from the Central Government. But the village infrastructure is still far from good but it is rather adequate for the community. This is because of the large village area so that not all road infrastructure in the village can be built due to budget constraints. Besides that,

it is also due to the high price of building materials, so it must save and prioritize the really important ones. This is because all road building materials that are used must be imported from outside the village, whereas there is no road access via land, so it must pass through the river and use a boat, which is what causes the high price of the material. All activities carried out are the result of village development planning deliberations.

3.4 The Village Expansion Policy towards Efforts to Improve Service to the Community of the Government Administration Services Sector

Regulating and managing the interests of the village community is certainly a necessity for the Village Government in the form of service to the community. Along with the increasing need of the community for administrative matters, the greater the demand for improvement in the quality of services provided, so that the services provided can be fast and precise, even though they will be satisfied with the services provided. To find out the extent of service quality and what is served and what obstacles are faced by the village government officials in providing administrative services to the community. Need research and know what kind of administration is given by the village government to the community as the object of the service.

Types of administrative services served by apparatuses Bantian village government are the General Administrative Services and Population Administration. The procedure for general administration and population administration services is service in the form of correspondence submitted by interested parties. The correspondence is in the form of a certificate, cover letter, and the legalization of letters. Service procedures should be regulated in the form of village regulations (Perdes). At the time of this study, the Perdes which regulated general administration and population services had not yet had a Perdes, as were the Perdes concerning village income (Perdes PAD) that had not yet been arranged. So that the service procedures provided by their apparatus do without any specific rules that become the reference and only run with a habitual pattern. Village original income from village administration services can be levied if the Perdes PAD exists and during the Perdes does not conflict with the rules above. Examples of administrative services that can be carried out are levies, certificates of sale and purchase, letters of land, certificates of building permits, etc. which are the authority of the village if there is a levy on services to the intended documents to the public. Levies on the people who receive administrative services as long as there is no legal basis for the types of services above are spontaneous or habitual. The current source of income for the village of Bantian comes from transfer funds only, namely from Village Fund (DD), the Village Fund Budget (ADD), and revenue sharing from regional taxes and levies.

Based on the results of interviews with the village secretary has been found that the obstacles that occur are village officials who have not mastered the use of computers, community service systems, procedures, and rules. The Bantian village community says that the work culture in the Bantian village government is still lacking

with the indiscipline of village officials in service, lack of work ethic, convoluted bureaucratic processes, poor-quality human resources, and village officials who work unprofessionally in their duties. Meanwhile, according to Pulau Hanaut District Chief, Bantian villagers now no longer need to go far away from the region just to take care of important letters, although according to him, service is still lacking because the executor does not understand information technology.

4. Discussion

4.1 Effectiveness of the Village Expansion Policy on Service Implementation in the Education Sector

The results of field observations and interviews with several speakers, the implementation of education after the expansion of the village has changed and some have not changed. These changes occurred in the implementation of education at the junior and senior high school levels as well as the addition of existing teachers who did not yet exist. Whereas those that have not changed are not the addition of new school buildings, and the implementation of education at the junior and senior high school levels using the elementary school building.

From the results of interviews with respondents as education providers, it was concluded that there was an increase in education at the junior and senior high school levels in Bantian village due to the Government's nine-year compulsory education policy, and educational implementation initiatives in this village. While the results of interviews with the organizers of the village expansion policy (Village Head) concluded that authority and village capacity were limited in the implementation of education, but with the village expansion policy, this policy could support the implementation of education in this village, this was evidenced by community dissertation in the form of proposals for development activities in the education sector, and the availability of village communities to grant land for the construction of new educational facilities. The construction of village roads also has a positive impact on the implementation of education in this village.

From the information above, it can be concluded that the improvement in the implementation of education in the village is effective for the target group because it can meet the needs of the target, and the village expansion policy is not effective for the implementation of education at a certain level due to the limited authority and capacity of the village. There is a need for other policies in the field of education so that these policies support each other to achieve the desired goals.

4.2 Effectiveness of the Village Expansion Policy on the Implementation of Health Services

The results of field observations and interviews with village communities, health cadres, health officers and Bantian village heads said that the construction of health facilities in Bantian village was following the village expansion policy, as a result of

interviews with representatives of the Bantian village community that the Pustu development in Bantian village after the expansion village, we are close to getting service. Furthermore, the results of interviews with health workers on duty after the presence of pustu in Bantian village said that there were still many obstacles faced in the health sector services in this village. Furthermore, the Bantian Village Head said that there was an increase in health services after the expansion of the village, although there were still many obstacles, and village authority in the health sector was only limited to the form of activity facilitation.

The results of the observation that there are still obstacles in providing health services so that the service has not been maximized to the target group. This situation shows that there is an increase in services compared to before the division of the village and there is still a need for other policies in the health sector carried out by the regional government as the authority holders so that health services to the community in this village can be better than the current situation. With village authority in the health sector, the village government through its policies can prioritize activities in the field of basic infrastructure including the health sector. The implementation of health services in the village is effective only for target groups that get services, and are still ineffective because in providing services there are many obstacles. In this case, a policy is not effective without other policies that accompany it.

4.3 Effectiveness of Village Expansion Policy towards the Implementation of Services in the Infrastructure Sector

The results of field observations with the results of interviews with village government organizers, that after the expansion of the village, the construction of village road infrastructure was greater when compared to before the expansion. This is due to the existence of a budget from the government which is directly managed directly by the village government. Every year Bantian village will always get a budget from the government that will be used to finance government administration, development, community development, and community empowerment.

Based on the results of the interviews with several resource persons, it can be concluded that the progress of the construction of road infrastructure facilities shows better when compared to the expansion. The village government can plan and implement the activities that will be carried out based on the ability and authority of the village in providing services in the infrastructure sector to the community. Infrastructure services and village expansion policies are effective for the target group because they can meet their needs, even though they are carried out in stages and cannot be implemented simultaneously by the village government, because of the limited budget received in each budget year.

4.4 The effectiveness of the Village Expansion Policy on the Implementation of Services in the Village Government Administration Sector

The services of the general administration and population to the community as the target group have been carried out by the Bantian village government, although in terms of service delivery there are still shortcomings that need to be completed and fulfilled by village government organizers. This shows that the village expansion policy is effective in public administration services and population to the community by the existing authority in the Village Government.

4.5 Efficiency of the Village Expansion Policy towards the Implementation of Services in the Education Sector

The results of observations conducted by researchers found that there are still many obstacles faced in the implementation of education in the village of Bantian, such as incomplete educational facilities and infrastructure at the level of education, at the junior and senior high school levels, simultaneously use and other facilities are elementary school buildings. The proposal for the construction of junior and senior high school buildings and the additional demand for civil servant teachers to the district government has not been realized. This shows an imbalance between the policies of the available resources. The thing that affects the relationship between the policy of village expansion and the policy of implementing education is that the village community has more opportunities in the effort to propose development activities in the education sector. The target group (community) gets more opportunities in channeling their aspirations.

From the results of interviews with the village head of Bantian, information was obtained that the village had the authority to administer early childhood education and the implementation of education outside of school and did not have the authority in terms of the implementation of education at the elementary, junior high, high school, etc. But with the expansion of the village, the village government can carry out its functions and authority in facilitating by its authority to support the implementation of education in the villages of Bantian. The village expansion policy is not efficient in administering education in the village, but the policy of implementing education in rural villages is more efficient with the existence of a village expansion policy because the village can facilitate the existence of such education implementation policies.

4.6 Efficiency of Village Expansion Policies on the Implementation of Health Services

Health services after the division in Bantian village have built health facilities in the form of pustu development by the district government and facilitated Posyandu activities by the village government. But in the implementation of service delivery, there are still many obstacles faced. This is due to the imbalance between service providers and those receiving services, and the imbalance of service facilities and infrastructure.

This shows an increase in health services compared to before the division. In terms of service efficiency, some people who are close to service find it easy and close to get services, on the other hand, there are still people who feel far from service because they are still far from other service sources and supporting facilities that are still not supported. The policy of village expansion with health service policies in Bantian villages shows the existence of interrelationships so that the objectives of the policy will be more efficient in achieving the objectives of the policy.

4.7 Efficiency of the Village Expansion Policy towards the Implementation of Services in the Infrastructure Sector

Based on the results of field observations and the results of interviews with informants, that every year the village of Bantian gets a budget for government administration, development, coaching, and community empowerment. In the field of village development, the village government has for several years prioritized the construction of village roads and bridges. The implementation of these activities was carried out based on the results of community proposals in the village discussion activities which were subsequently included in the development activities document in the Village Budget (APBDes). This shows that the policy of expansion of villages is efficient towards rural communities as a policy target. Because by being a village, the village will get a budget (fund) from the government that is used by the priority needs of development that comes from the proposals of the village community.

4.8 Efficiency of the Village Expansion Policy towards Services in the Field of Village Government Administration Services

As a new village was formed, there were still many shortcomings in the village apparatus in providing services to the target communities and communities that received services. This was due to the lack of apparatus and infrastructure and the ability of the apparatus to provide services. But at least various general administration and population services have been carried out and the village community does not feel far away to get services in the field of general administration and population. There needs to be an increase in village apparatus resources in the field of administrative services, by including village officials in administrative training activities to increase capacity in terms of service delivery.

4.9 Adequacy of Village Expansion Policies on Education Services

In his theory, Willian N. Dunn, argues that sufficiency by how far a degree of effectiveness satisfies the needs, values or opportunities that grow problems. This shows that adequacy is related to effectiveness by measuring how to predict how far the alternative can satisfy the needs, values or opportunities in solving the problems that occur. The following is a discussion regarding the public service impact of the expansion of Bantian village, Pulau Hanaut District, East Kotawaringin Regency.

Services in the education sector in Bantian village after the expansion of the village as explained above have increased as an explanation of the theory of adequacy, when effectiveness and efficiency can meet satisfaction in a policy. As the explanation on both of these (Effectiveness and Efficiency), that education policy at the specified level is the policy of implementing education outside the village expansion policy, but the two policies are series of relationships because they support one another. In this case, about the implementation of education in the village and reading the results of the discussion on effectiveness and efficiency, the implementation of education in this village is sufficient for the target, because they feel that they have educational services that are close to the target, cheap and in their village. While the policy of village expansion is not enough to meet the target needs in the field of education services, because it does not have the authority and ability to carry out education at the advanced level and still requires the existence of education policies implemented in the village.

4.10 Adequacy of Village Expansion Policies for Health Services

As well as the adequacy of services in the field of education so is the case in services in the health sector. The existence of the village expansion policy encouraged the district government to make other policies to support this policy. The construction of Pustu and other health facilities in Bantian village as a new village as a result of the village expansion policy is another government policy other than the village expansion policy. This shows the inadequacy of a policy without other policies to meet the needs of the community as a target. In connection with the implementation of health in Bantian village the target group feels they have fulfilled their needs, because the service already exists and is close to them. While the policy of village expansion cannot be sufficient for health services, there is, therefore, a need for policies in the health sector that are implemented in this village to meet the adequacy of health services in this village.

4.11 Adequacy of Village Expansion Policies for Infrastructure Services

The village expansion policy and the implementation of the implementation, the village community is the target group of the village policy. In terms of the adequacy of service in the field of village infrastructure, the community as the group served feels a certain satisfaction after the policy is implemented. It is known that the village expansion policy is effective and efficient in implementing infrastructure services. Even though other policies are still needed in the field of infrastructure beyond what the village can do to implement it. The community as the target group feels sufficient because by making it a village, the village will get its budget in the event of infrastructure development in their village. This is by the results of field observations, that the construction of roads and bridges is one of the village infrastructures that has been implemented. The proposed activity is planned to be carried out by the community itself. Although it was carried out in a phased manner due to budget constraints, the

community felt that the certainty of infrastructure development (roads and bridges) in their villages could be fulfilled as time went on according to the stages.

4.12 Adequacy of Village Expansion Policies towards the Service of the Village Government Administration Sector

At the level of community satisfaction as the target of this policy, services in the field of service have not shown the satisfaction they feel. This is because in providing services there are still many weaknesses in apparatus resources in providing services. Although it has been carried out by service providers (village officials). But at least there is another satisfaction felt by the target group (community) because they feel close and do not need to be far away from the parent to get service. As explained earlier, it was said that the village expansion policy was effective and efficient towards the services of the general administration and population. This is the adequacy in providing services to the target group. The problem is the apparatus resources that still need to get increased capacity in providing services and facilities for village apparatus that need to be improved in the provision of facilities and infrastructure to support the performance of village officials.

4.13 Targeted Responsivity

As the theory put forward by William N. Dunn, that responsiveness is how far a policy can satisfy the needs, pretensions or values of the target group. The success of a policy can be seen through the response of the target group (community) after the impact can be felt. The response can be in the form of a positive form of support, or a negative form of rejection. In this case, William N Dunn suggests that the criteria for target responsiveness are important because this analysis can satisfy all other criteria (effectiveness, efficiency, and adequacy), still fail if they have not responded to the actual needs of the target group that should benefit from the existence of such a policy.

As explained earlier, services in the fields of education, health, infrastructure, and general administration and population sectors show an increase compared to before the existence of village division. in the field of education at the advanced level (junior and senior high school) has been held and the number of teachers teaching in Bantian villages has increased. In the field of health services public health facilities have been built and are assigned by health workers to Bantian village, infrastructure built as roads, bridge rehabilitation, construction of bridge bridges continuously from year to year, and in the field of public administration and population services, the community gets service and closer and affordable than before.

Each field of service does indeed show progress as an increase from the previous situation. Satisfaction occurs when the desires of the community are fulfilled, in this case, the Bantian and surrounding hamlets can be realized as villages. This can be realized and an increase in the effect development activities of the policy after it is implemented. While the shortcomings that occur in the provision of services that occur

are not too influential on their satisfaction, because the target group feels that the existence of certainty and deficiencies will be fulfilled gradually.

4.14 Policy Evaluation

According to Winarno (2007) policy evaluation is an attempt to determine the impact on a policy on real-life conditions in the target group (community). This can be understood as an attempt to determine the impact or frequency of what happens in the policy. While Dunn explained that in policy evaluation distinguishes the consequences of policies in two types, namely output and impact, output is goods, services or other facilities received by a particular group of people, both target groups and other groups that are not intended to be touched by policy, whereas impact is physical and social conditions as a result of policy output.

Impact evaluation gives greater attention to the output of policy impacts than to the implementation process itself. The expected impact is a positive impact and an unexpected impact is a negative impact. Furthermore, in the evaluation study of Finterbusch and Motz, there were several evaluation studies that he presented. One of them is the evaluation study with the term Rafter program singlet which examines the impact that has been made on the implementation of the policy and after the implementation of the policy also observes the situation of the target group before and after the policy program is implemented. An explanation of the effectiveness, efficiency, adequacy, and responsiveness of the expansion of the Bantian village policy in the previous discussion shows that two impacts occurred in the implementation of the policy. As the explanation of the theory described above are the positive impact and negative impact of a policy. The positive impact is felt when the policy can change the previous situation to be better and show improvement. The increase received a positive response from the target group (community).

While the negative impact is, there is public dissatisfaction with the service, because there are still obstacles in providing services. These constraints are the government's lack of response to the proposed activities proposed by the community, the construction of village facilities and infrastructure that have not been thoroughly integrated into remote areas of the village, programs, and activities carried out in stages due to limited budgets, and still weak apparatus resources. Furthermore, it is similar to the situation before and after the expansion of the village, as the theory put forward by Finterbusch and Motz, "*the singlet before Rafter program*". Bantian village, in general, shows better improvement than the previous situation due to the impact of the expansion of the village.

5. Conclusion

- 1) The policy of village division is ineffective, inefficient and inadequate for services in the fields of education and services in the health sector due to limited authority and budget, but with the expansion of villages there has been an

increase in services in both fields due to the policies in education and the health sector accompanying village governance policies.

- 2) The policy of the expansion of the village towards the services of infrastructure and services in the field of general administration and population in the village is effective, efficient and sufficient for the target group. Krama will gradually be able to meet the target needs.
- 3) In implementing the village division policy, the satisfaction felt by the target group is when their main desires are fulfilled and other policies that accompany the village policy.
- 4) The positive impact felt by the target group is that the policy can change the previous situation to be better because of the increase in various service fields. While the negative impact occurs after the implementation is running, this is because there is still a sense of community dissatisfaction with the services they get, which is because there are still many obstacles faced in the service obtained by the target.

5.1 Recommendations

- 1) There is a need for other policies from the government that support each other for the policy of village expansion so that the policy will be effective, efficient and sufficient and get better respiration from the target group (community).
- 2) The target group (community) is not always dependent on the government as the policyholder, and shows independence through increasing human resource capacity and the utilization of natural resources in the village.

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